

Exploring the Dynamics of Agripreneurship Perception and Intention among the Nigerian Youth

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture is a strategic sector for tackling the perennial problem of youth unemployment in Nigeria. However, lack of youth participation has hampered the growth of agriculture. This study investigates the dynamics of agripreneurship perception and intention while exploring agricultural entrepreneurship as a valuable functioning among the Nigerian youth.

The study engaged both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. The quantitative analysis was conducted using linear regression and multinomial response models. Moreover, Sen's capability approach formed the theoretical foundation for the work.

The results established that the Nigerian youths display a positive perception and intention towards agripreneurship engagement. It also found that course of study, participation in entrepreneurship programs, family income status, perceived availability of markets and infrastructural facilities are determinants of youth agripreneurship perception and intention. Moreover, the study found that the need to eradicate poverty, opportunity to express one's passion, and freedom to control one's time are reasons young Nigerians value agripreneurship.

This study serves as a debut of research endeavours that theoretically evaluates agricultural entrepreneurship as a valuable functioning through the lens of capability approach. Furthermore, by x-raying factors that affect agripreneurship perception and intention, the study offers fresh policy insights for youth agricultural entrepreneurship development.

Keywords: Agriculture, Capability approach, Entrepreneurial perception, Entrepreneurial intention, Youth unemployment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is endowed with numerous resources including expansive fertile agricultural land and abundant mineral deposits (Omotola 2008). It is also Africa's largest economy, with growing financial, manufacturing, service, agriculture, communications, entertainment and technology sectors (Abubakar et al., 2022). Unfortunately, the country still relies on crude oil as its primary source of government revenues and foreign exchange earnings (Central Intelligence Agency 2020), making its economy vulnerable to the volatility of the oil price. With an increasing rate of unemployment, Nigeria is currently a poverty capital of the world with 133 million Nigerians (63%) living in poverty (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Although Nigeria is blessed with a highly energetic youth population, they are disproportionately affected by the unemployment crisis. The National Bureau of Statistics (2020) noted that as of the last quarter of 2020, the youth unemployment/underemployment rate was 63.1%. The consequences of this high youth unemployment include extreme poverty, armed robbery, kidnapping, thuggery, terrorism and political instability (World Bank 2019).

Entrepreneurship is considered a potent force for socioeconomic development, with young people at the fulcrum (Omeje et al., 2020). In agriculture, entrepreneurship deals with identifying opportunities across the value chains and marshalling the resources towards exploiting the opportunities, thereby creating value while reaping the attendant rewards. This concept is encapsulated in the word "agripreneurship," a portmanteau of agriculture and entrepreneurship.

Agriculture has been identified as a strategic sector to be leveraged in boosting employment opportunities for the Nigerian youth (Lyocks et al., 2013; Adesina & Favour 2016). However, production challenges have hampered the growth of the sector. For instance, the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (2020) observed that Nigeria loses 10 billion dollars in annual export opportunity from groundnut, cocoa palm oil and cotton alone due to continuous decline in the production of these commodities. Moreover, Nigeria has an underdeveloped agro-industrial sector exporting raw agricultural commodities and importing finished goods (Oxford Business Group 2019). Fortunately, the challenges of the agric sector indicate massive opportunities for young entrepreneurs to step in, identify market frictions and convert them into business opportunities thereby enhancing productivity and job creation.

However, it has been observed that the sector is beleaguered by protracted youth apathy which arises from the adversative perception and poor judgement of Nigerian youth towards the Agric sector in general. For instance, Adesina & Favour (2016) point out that arising from the array of challenges militating against the development of agriculture in Nigeria, the sector appears unattractive and non-lucrative to many youths, thus discouraging the smooth absorption of the youth into strategic agricultural undertakings in Nigeria and Africa in general.

This study investigated the perception of young Nigerians towards agric entrepreneurship and their intention to start agribusinesses. It further explores agric entrepreneurship as a valuable functioning among the Nigeria youth. Using Sen's capability approach, the research offers a comprehensive framework through which youth agricultural entrepreneurship perception and intention can be maximised in a bid to ameliorate the rising scourge of youth unemployment in Nigeria.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research adopted a combination of quantitative and qualitative methodologies which has been referred to as a mixed research method. Essentially, the primary qualitative data were collected through the use of an online survey (open ended questions) and semi-structured interview, while the primary quantitative data were collected with the aid of online survey questionnaires. The essence of the qualitative data collection was to allow the participants to freely express their view, perception and intention on agricultural entrepreneurship in the context of Nigeria, while the quantitative data were extracted with a view to quantitatively estimating the coefficients of the respective determinants of both of youth agripreneurship perception and intention with further evidence from Nigeria. In addition, the entire data collection (interview and survey administration) took place from March, 2020 to April 2021.

Using purposeful sampling method, eight (8) interviewees were engaged during the semi-structured interview process and the selected interviewees comprised four (4) established agripreneurs (2 male and 2 female), who are thriving in different areas of the agricultural value chain, four (4) recent graduates who are potential agripreneurs consisting of 2 male and 2 female, as well as one (1) entrepreneurship educator/expert with comprehensive experience in several youth Agric intervention programmes. This particular interviewee was highly instrumental in providing a holistic angle to the subject.

The sampling frame for the quantitative study involves recent graduates in Nigeria that were currently undertaking their one-year National Youth Service, those that have graduated but awaiting their National Youth Service posting or have successfully completed their one-year National Youth Service at most six (6) months prior to the questionnaire survey. The motivation for the choice of young graduates is that they must have gone through entrepreneurship education, which is now a compulsory course/module in all Nigerian tertiary institutions (Onuma, 2016) and the fact that these young Nigerian graduates would either seek work or start a business after their one-year National Youth Service. The study used a combination of stratified and snowball sampling techniques. To ensure the sample is evenly distributed across the country, the total population was partitioned into six (6) different strata, with each stratum representing a geopolitical zone and in each geopolitical zone, a snowball sampling technique was used to reach participants. Altogether, a sample of 1000 youth was drawn from the 1.2 million recent graduates who fall within the study frame.

The coding process followed a progressive order from "5" to "1" as the responses swing from strongly agrees to strongly disagree.

2.1 Linear regression model

The linear regression model in equation (1) was adopted for forecasting youth perception of agriculture entrepreneurship given a set of explanatory variables (Montgomery, Peck, and Vining 2013).

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Where; Y is the dependent variable, $X_1 \dots X_k$ are the independent variables, β = regression coefficients to be estimated ϵ = error term in the model.

2.2 Multinomial response model

Also, the intention to participate in agripreneurship was assessed based on the same set of variables captured in the perception model above using a multinomial response/multinomial logistic regression model adopted in Manda et al. (2021).

$$\log(Y) = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

While equation 1 was used to estimate the impact of selected factors on youth perception of agripreneurship, equation 2 on the other hand was used to estimate the impact of the selected factors on youth agripreneurship intention. Where; Y=polytomous outcome (A series/variable with more than two separate options or categories), $\text{Logit}(Y)$ =natural logarithm of the odds of Y (youth agripreneurship participation), B_1, \dots, B_k and α are as defined above, X_1, \dots, X_k are the independent/explanatory variables such as institutional and financial support, government support, markets for agricultural products, course of study, infrastructure etc.

2.3 Data analytical technique

First, the quantitative and qualitative data were analysed using SPSS (V. 24.0) and ATLAS.ti 9 respectively.

2.4 Ethics considerations

The study was approved by the University of the Western Cape Senate, the Faculty of Economics and Management Sciences Board, and the Institute for Social Development. The participants were duly informed about the implication of the study and their permission sought before engaging them in the process. Also data collected was treated with anonymity and strict confidentiality.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship development is considered as a potent force for stimulating economic growth and employment generation (Polas et al., 2022). On the other hand, Adeyanju et al. (2021) observe that for developing countries like Nigeria, the agricultural sector offers great opportunities to be harnessed by youth participation through the instrumentality of entrepreneurship. In order to fully maximise Nigeria's Agric sector, the energies and talents of young people must be engaged (Pelzom & Katel, 2018; Adeyanju et al., 2021).

The poor youth engagement in agriculture stems from numerous obstacles that make agriculture economically unappealing to them. For instance, Nnadi & Akwiwu (2008) observed that educational attainment, parents' work, and parents' farm income affect agricultural participation while Ahaibwe et al. (2013) revealed that access to improved farming resources (like quality seeds), which would enhance productivity and profitability affect agricultural engagement. Similarly, found that youth agricultural participation is hampered by lack of education, poor/lack of modern working tools, poor marketing system, and inadequate infrastructures. Moreover, Adesina & Favour (2016) identified inadequate training facilities, low profit margin, lack of agricultural equipment and machinery as constraints to youth agric participation.

According to Adeyanju et al. (2021), the level of agribusiness training significantly affects the performance of young entrepreneurs in agricultural activities. Scholars like Inegbedion & Islam (2021) and Mkong et al. (2021) found that participation in agripreneurship among undergraduates is influenced by the

family home location with a positive perception when a family home is located in the rural area, due to the likelihood of gaining access to land for agricultural production.

A number of scholars have acknowledged the role of perception in moderating the intention of youth in entrepreneurship engagement in both developed and emerging economies. For instance, Cheteni (2016) found that low youth agricultural engagement stems from negative perceptions young people have towards agriculture which they often see as an unattractive sector. In the same vein, Njeru et al. (2015) affirmed the existence of a statistically significant positive relationship between youth perception of agriculture and active agripreneurship participation. Also Priyaraj (2017); Mukembo (2017); Ng'atigwa et al. (2020) established that perceived capabilities significantly influence the decision of individuals to take up an occupation.

According to Adeyanju (2021), perception about the benefit of agripreneurship training and agribusiness affects the success of agripreneurship participation. On the other hand, Shidiq (2020) established that attitudes, individuals' characteristics, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural influences of agricultural students predicts their intention to participate in agripreneurship, while Ikuemonisan & Akinbola (2021) found that students' perceptions about learning and age exerted a significant influence on the likelihood of their participation in agripreneurial activities.

While a number of studies have investigated youth agricultural perception and participation in different parts of Nigeria, there is little or no study providing a nationwide assessment of the disposition of young people towards agricultural entrepreneurship. Furthermore, none of the available studies engaged the capability approach which is considered a comprehensive framework for analyzing issues. Thus, apart from offering a more recent insight into youth agripreneurship engagement, this study provides a nationwide view of the situation while engaging a comprehensive framework. The study further explores agricultural entrepreneurship as a valuable functioning among young Nigerians.

3.1 Sen's capability approach

This study utilised Sen's capability approach as the theoretical framework. Sen's theory places greater emphasis on the intrinsic value of humans which can be boosted through the expansion of the individual's capabilities in the course of national development. Sen maintains that an individual's freedom to lead a life he/she has reason to value should be the central aim of development while economic measures should be seen as an avenue to actualise this. In this way, the capability approach emphasises the available opportunities or freedoms (known as capabilities) for a person to achieve various beings and doings which he/she has reason to value (known as functionings). The achieved functionings of a person refer to those capabilities which the person has pursued and realised successfully (Alkire 2008). For instance, a graduate who is successfully running an Agribusiness can be said to have achieved the functioning of being an agripreneur. Thus, the capability approach serves as a theoretical perspective which can be used as a practical tool for evaluating institutions, policies, services and social arrangements.

3.1.1 Conversion factors in agripreneurship participation: Sen highlighted the critical role of personal, social and environmental conversion factors in a person's effort to translate a particular resource(s) into achieved functioning. For example, a patriarchal culture (social conversion factor) can inhibit a girl's agency or sense of ability to undertake Agric entrepreneurship (Roomi et al., 2018).

3.1.2 Application of the capability approach to agripreneurship: In recent years, there has been a lot of focus on getting young Nigerians into agricultural entrepreneurship as a means of effectively tackling the perennial challenge of youth unemployment. While this is undoubtedly a step in the right direction, little emphasis is placed on the available capabilities (opportunities) for the youth to engage in and succeed in agricultural venture creation. Thus, being a comprehensive framework, the capability approach can shed light on various factors that are critical to ensuring real success for young and aspiring agripreneur.

3.1.3 Agripreneurship as a Valued Functioning: Considering the impact of entrepreneurial motivation on business success (Amit & Muller, 1995), it is important to understudy agripreneurship as a valued functioning among the youth. Among other things, this will help to answer the question of whether young

Nigerians have reason to value agric entrepreneurship. Moreover, it can also provide a deeper insight on why agricultural engagement is not favoured by the youth.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

4.1 Analysis of Youth Agripreneurship Perception in Nigeria

Youth agripreneurship perception implies the way in which the youth value, understand, or interpret agripreneurship based on personal, environmental and social variables surrounding the individual. The study analysed the perception of the youth towards agricultural entrepreneurship by examining whether the participants view agriventure as a business for the poor and uneducated, or whether they see it as stressful, highly capital intensive, risky or a lucrative venture. The findings established that 75.80% of the youth disagree with the notion that agripreneurship is for the poor. Thus, most of the youth believe that agribusiness can be embraced by people of various socioeconomic strata.

Similarly, 77% of the participants rejected the idea that agripreneurship is only meant for students with intellectual deficiency. The implication of this is that the youth have come to see good opportunities in the sector. It is not just for those with poor academic standing, but also for people who are intellectually sound. Given the level of their mental alertness, the youth have the potential to identify frictions across agro value chains and innovate solutions to them, thereby driving the nation's economy through agripreneurship involvement.

Another finding from the survey is that about 74.90% of the participants were in disagreement with the notion that agripreneurship is only suitable for people with no or low educational background. The result suggests that most of the youth investigated during the survey are likely to consider agripreneurship as a viable option, citing their level of education and the entrepreneurship skills they have acquired during and after their tertiary education. Apart from other conversion factors, their exposure to entrepreneurship education and the knowledge they acquired during their undergraduate years might have shaped this perception.

Also, about 75.40% of the participants dispelled the idea that agripreneurship is risky, notwithstanding the occasional shocks from adverse weather conditions (Olowe, 2021; Raheem et al., 2021), inadequate infrastructure, poor quality of available input resources (like feeds for aquaculture, seeds, etc), price instability of both input materials and final produce, poor research and development effort, transportation and logistics challenges, etc. (Olukunle, 2013; Adesina & Favour 2016; Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2020).

Also, about 78.80% of the respondents didn't perceive agribusiness to be highly capital intensive. This demonstrates the fact that even with little start-up capital, they believe that they can establish and manage an agric venture.

In summary, it can be established that, subject to the sample size and the period this survey was conducted, the Nigerian youth have a positive disposition towards agripreneurship. This overall finding on positive youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria contradicts Fabiyi et al. (2015) who found a negative perception about agricultural undertakings. The change in perception may be due to several agricultural initiatives and programmes being implemented by the government and non-state actors to enhance youth participation in agripreneurship. This assertion is in line with the response of one of the interview participants who noted that'; *"The participation, if I were to measure, is increasing based on the various programmes that have been initiated by the government. There is enough incentive for young people to participate in agriculture."*

Furthermore, the participants perceived that agriculture is a viable tool for employment generation for the youth and this drives their intention and active participation in agripreneurship. This might have also impacted their agripreneurship perception. For instance, one of the participants during the interview submitted that: *"based on the fact that there are limited job opportunities, Nigerian youths are being encouraged to be job creators rather than job seekers and there are several schemes by both the government and non-state actors to support young people in the space"*.

The increasing level of positive youth agripreneurship perception from the quantitative analysis is in tandem with the qualitative finding. For example, an interviewee who is an Agric expert/educator submitted as follows:

“My opinion about the space is that it has provided employment for a lot of people who otherwise will have been unemployed. Yes, because most graduates in Nigeria have no jobs. And also, for young people who do not have formal tertiary education, the promotion of agriculture as the future of entrepreneurship and work in Nigeria has encouraged them to venture into the agriculture space whereas before now, such people who do not have tertiary education would have been feeling inadequate or looking for menial jobs. Now, they are looking at opportunities in agribusiness and starting up small ventures. So, for me I think it is a very good space for creating a lot of employment opportunities for young people. Both those who have formal tertiary education and those who do not.”

Another respondent who is also an existing agripreneur revealed the following;

“If we look at the demographic challenges we are having especially with young Africans and the amount of investment they are able to receive from their family and the government, agriculture is naturally the right way to start..... We need to create opportunities outside megacities and Agriculture provides a path to do so.”

Thus, agricultural entrepreneurship can serve as a cure for the rural-urban migration which has exacerbated unemployment and resource constraints in urban cities (Obayelu et al., 2020)

Generally speaking, the qualitative interview corroborates the findings from the quantitative survey as young people increasingly perceive desirable opportunities in agriculture. As noted by a recent graduate, *“agriculture business is not for the poor people. In fact, it is a lucrative business, and many people tend not to understand what agriculture is all about....I wish the youths can see that it is not just for the poor people or the uneducated ones”* (Table 1).

Table 1. Youth perception about agricultural entrepreneurship

Statements	Neutral	Disagree
Agriculture business is for the poor	24.20%	75.80%
Entrepreneurship is for dull students	23%	77%
Agriculture business is for the uneducated	25.10%	74.90%
Agric business is risky	24.60%	75.40%
Agric business is highly capital intensive	21.20%	78.80%

4.2 Factors responsible youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria

Table 2 reports estimates from the linear regression analysis. From the result, it was established that undergraduate course of study, participation in entrepreneurship training programs, family income status, perceived availability of markets for agricultural products as well as availability of infrastructural facilities were the significant determinants of youth agripreneurship perception in the period of assessment.

4.3 Course of study and youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria

The result showed that all other things being equal, positive youth agripreneurship perception is approximately 1.07 units higher on average among youth who studied an agriculture related course than those who had a degree in non-agriculture related score. This is statistically significant at 95% confidence level. It therefore follows that when the number of youths who studied agriculture related courses during their undergraduate programme increases, there will be a corresponding increase in the number of youths who hold a positive view of agripreneurship. This finding aligns Mkong et al. (2021) who disclosed that students’ penchant for agricultural entrepreneurship is significantly influenced by their current academic engagement. Similarly, Inegbedion & Islam (2021) noted that most of the undergraduate youth currently taking a course in agriculture are influenced by their perceived ability to effectively manage an agribusiness as well as perceived impact of agriculture on their career progression.

4.4 Entrepreneurship programmes and youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria

The perception score among the youth who participate in an entrepreneurship programme will increase by about 2.11 units compared to those who are yet to participate in the program. This is statistically

significant at 99% confidence level, and indicative of the fact that the knowledge and skills acquired in the course of the various entrepreneurship and skills acquisition programmes will help shape the agripreneurship perception of the participants (Adeyanju et al., 2021). This could also be attributed to the fact that these young Nigerians might have been exposed to the dynamics of agripreneurship in the course of their Skills Acquisition and Entrepreneurship Development (SAED) programme. Specifically, the NYSC SAED on Agriculture offers such unique opportunities to serving Corps Members during the mandatory post-graduation National Youth Service period.

Table 2. Agripreneurship perception

Parameter	B	Std. Error	t	Sig.
Intercept	36.120***	0.909	39.738	0.000
Undergraduate Course				
Agric	1.070**	0.420	2.550	0.011
Non-Agric	0 ^a			
Family Income Background				
Poor	4.123***	0.616	6.699	0.000
Low Income	2.953***	0.395	7.473	0.000
Middle Income	2.804***	0.375	7.472	0.000
Upper Income	0 ^a			
Participation in Agric Intervention Program				
Yes	-0.175	0.295	-0.592	0.554
No	0 ^a			
Participation in Agric Entrepreneurship Prog				
Yes	2.109***	0.397	5.311	0.000
No	0 ^a			
Lack of Government Support	-0.225	0.180	-1.249	0.212
Lack of Financial Support	0.218	0.183	1.193	0.233
Lack of Market for Agric Produce	-0.651***	0.142	-4.589	0.000
Lack of Agric Infrastructure	0.489***	0.163	3.005	0.003

Note: *, **, *** implies significance at 10%, 5% and 1% significance level respectively.

4.5 Household income status and youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria

This study revealed that youth agripreneurship perception decreased with increasing levels of household's income. Thus, those from relatively poor families were associated with higher positive agripreneurship perception scores than those from the low-income, middle-income and wealthy or upper income class.

4.6 Market for agricultural products and youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria

The result shows that a significant negative relationship exists between lack of market for Agro-products and youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria. When the perceived lack of Market for farm produce increases by 1 unit, youth positive agripreneurship perception declines by 0.679 units. Thus, a significant expansion in the market for Agro-products may lead to a more positive agripreneurship perception while lack of market opportunities may engender a negative effect.

As noted by one of the interviewees:

“There is no accessibility into the market... Little things like this tend to bring one's morale down. In developed countries like the United States for example, even before they plant, they know the amount they will sell their produce. But in Nigeria, you cannot even project. By the time you harvest, you will start looking for buyers....”.

4.7 Infrastructure and youth agripreneurship perception in Nigeria

The study found the relationship between infrastructural deficiency and youth agripreneurship perception to be positive, suggesting the more the youth hold the perception that there is lack of infrastructure for agriculture business the better their perception about agriculture entrepreneurship. This result contradicts theoretical apriori expectation since the entire agricultural value chain requires access to critical infrastructure and certain Agro-processing technologies to boost productivity in the system (Lyocks et al., 2013; Shiwa 2014; Jha et al., 2020)

The quantitative finding also contradicts the response of an interviewee, who noted that,

“Infrastructure remains a major challenge. Sometimes when it rains, roads to the farm are not accessible. Customers would try to avoid coming to the farm, no one would want to come to the farm because the roads are bad, and they do not want their trucks and cars to get stuck. Many of the transporters at this point would increase the fee because they already projected damages to their vehicle on the road. ”

While the findings on the quantitative finding on infrastructure seem counterintuitive, one may see the lack of infrastructure deficiency as an incentive to innovate solutions to tackle these issues. Taking this line of thought, it may appear that the Nigerian youth might have taken their destiny into their hands so that identified constraints are converted into opportunities in the entire agricultural value chain.

4.8 Other Findings

The study found that government support, institutional and financial support, technological infrastructure, agriculture intervention programme, tribe, gender and geopolitical zones had no significant effect on youth agripreneurship perception. Further details are shown on Table 2.

4.9 Analysis of youth agripreneurship intention in Nigeria

The perception of young Nigerians towards agripreneurship should have implications for their intention to actively participate in agribusiness. This is because no rational human would want to be involve himself/herself with something that is largely perceived to be disadvantageous This is also in tandem with the theory of planned behaviour which states that one's beliefs about attitude, control, and norms influence his/her behaviour (Kautonen et al., 2015). Thus, a positive perception will likely lead to positive intention. When asked about the intention to start an Agribusiness in the nearest future, the result showed that 75.1% of the participants were affirmative about commencing a business, while 9.3% had no interest in setting up such a venture. On the other hand, 15.6% of the participants were uncertain about taking such a decision.

4.10 Factors responsible for youth agripreneurship intention in Nigeria

An interesting fact about the outputs of the logistic regression analysis is that most of the findings are analogous to the results obtained in the analysis of the determinants of youth agripreneurship perception. For instance, the result showed that participation in entrepreneurship training programs, availability of market for agriculture products, family income background, were found to be significant determinants of youth intention to start an agribusiness.

However, while an inverse relationship exists between the family income background of the Nigerian youth and the perception about agripreneurship, the relationship between family income background and intention to start the business is direct, i.e. young people with richer family are more likely to start an agribusiness than youth from a poor family. Table 3 shows that the likelihood that youth will venture into an Agric business decreases by 0.971 units if he/she is from a poor family than those from the upper-income family on average, all other things being equal. This further implies that the youth perception about agriculture business does not automatically translate into intention to launch an agribusiness as far as the family income background is concerned. As noted earlier, a student from a poor family background may

have positive perception towards agricultural entrepreneurship due to his/her family farming experience but at the same time express lower intention due to the lack of financial capability to start a business.

Table 3. Factors responsible for youth agripreneurship intention

Agriculture Entrepreneurship Intention	Variables	B	Std. Error	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)
Yes	Intercept	2.495***	0.838	8.872	0.003	
	Lack of Government Support	0.091	0.168	0.293	0.588	1.095
	No financial support	0.126	0.172	0.541	0.462	1.135
	No market for agric produce	-0.368***	0.142	6.732	0.009	0.692
	lack of Infrastructure	-0.113	0.162	0.484	0.487	0.893
	Gender					
	Male	0.227	0.253	0.804	0.370	1.254
	Female(Ref)	0 ^b				
	Tribe					
	Hausa	-0.753**	0.373	4.074	0.044	0.471
	Igbo	-0.817**	0.373	4.806	0.028	0.442
	Others	-0.544	0.354	2.364	0.124	0.581
	Yoruba(Ref)	0 ^b				
	Course of Study					
	Agric-Related	0.237	0.405	0.342	0.559	1.267
	Non-Agric(Base)	0 ^b				
	Family Income Category					
	Poor	-0.971**	0.482	4.059	0.044	0.379
	Lower-Income	-0.383	0.364	1.104	0.293	0.682
	Middle-Income	-0.308	0.351	0.766	0.381	0.735
	Upper Income	0 ^b				
	Participation in Agric Intervention Program					
	Yes	0.367	0.255	2.074	0.150	1.443
	No (Ref)	0 ^b				
	Participation in Entrepreneurship Training Program					
	Yes	1.330***	0.273	23.672	0.000	3.781
	No (Ref)	0 ^b				

Note: *, **, *** implies significance at 10%, 5% and 1% significance level respectively.

Sen's capability approach highlights the role of personal, social and environmental conversion factors in a person's bid to translate the characteristics of a particular resource(s) into achieved functioning. In the situation while a person might have been predisposed (perhaps due to being raised in a rural or poor family) to have a positive perception of agricultural entrepreneurship, his or her decision to actually venture into the business (functioning) may be hampered by lack of the environmental conversion factor of financial constraints. Thus, viewed through the capability lens, for an entrepreneurship programme to be effective, it should go beyond improving perception to actually making sure that financial and other hurdles are removed from the path towards agriprenurship. This is in alignment with another study who found that among other things, increasing a household's annual income exhibited a statistically significant influence on the agriprenural decisions among the youth. This role of conversion factors is well indicated in the expanded model for Agriprenurship Participation (Fig. 1).

4.11 Exploring agricultural entrepreneurship as a valuable functioning

The theoretical framework of this study (Sen's capability approach) emphasises the concept of functioning which serves as a major drive agriprenurship engagement. As noted earlier, functioning are the various valuable doings and beings (Conradie, 2013). The concept encapsulates a series of activities and circumstances which are cherished by individuals who engage in them. Expanding the opportunity for these doings and beings is the focus of the capability approach. An example of a functioning is being able to launch an agribusiness or being an agriprenur.

In this study, the major emphasis is on the factors that motivate people to venture into agriprenurship. That is, what makes agricultural entrepreneurship a valuable being and ding (functioning)? In the course of the survey, a number of such factors were established as key stimuli for starting agribusiness. These include the need to eradicate poverty/malnutrition, opportunity to express one's passion/interest, freedom/be one's own boss/control your time, among others.

4.12 Agricultural entrepreneurship and the need for poverty and malnutrition eradication

One of the factors that propel people to venture in agricultural entrepreneurship is the need to eradicate the rising spate of poverty and malnutrition.

Source: Adapted from Robeyns (2005)

Figure 1. An expanded model for agriprenurship participation

This implies some people derive value from being able to contribute towards poverty and malnutrition eradication through agriculture. As noted by the following respondent:

“First, I came from a poverty background, and growing up I realised and understood that there is a need to produce foods at a cheap level. Secondly, I also observed that there is low quality of food producing firms in Nigeria. Why? because there is no standardization and regulation for the companies and people also do not really care about what they eat. One of the motivations is to provide quality and nutritious foods for people in Nigeria. These are the two major factors that motivated me into that field. Another one is the need for food security. No one can stay actually without food.”

The above finding is in tandem with the findings of scholars like Bairwa et al. (2014) who argue that people venture into agriculture with the aim of eradicating poverty since they will be able to provide food and generate income to meet their daily necessities.

4.13 Agricultural entrepreneurship as an opportunity to express one’s passion/interest

Aside from the need to tackle the menace of poverty and malnutrition, agricultural entrepreneurship also serves as an opportunity to express one’s passion/interest. For instance, an individual can develop significant interest in a specific aspect of agriculture like beekeeping, fish farming, pig farming, poultry farming etc. On the other hand, an individual may have specific interest in areas of crop production such as cereals and pulses (like garden peas) and Perennial crops (such as sugarcane, tea, coffee), and Field crops (such as tea and sugarcane farming). Thus, agricultural entrepreneurship offers individuals an opportunity to undertake their passion/interest (functioning). As indicated in the following responses:

“When I started, I could say I stumbled into my passion a few years ago, I think 2015, when I came back from the United States. Later on, I saw an advert relating to farming - poultry farming precisely. I believe then that it would be a lot of fun... I am passionate about Agric business, I have learnt a lot, but I would not totally agree I am enjoying it. But I am passionate about it.”

This is in tandem with Kabwe et al. (2018) who noted that, even in the face of inevitable difficulties along the journey, passion makes agric entrepreneurs persevere in their enterprises (Kabwe et al. 2018).

4.14 Agricultural entrepreneurship as an opportunity to express one’s freedom

Another notable fact about Agricultural Entrepreneurship as a value functioning is that it offers a unique opportunity for individuals to express their Freedom (Hatammimi & Wulandari, 2014). For instance, when participating in agriprenurship, people have the privilege of acting as their own boss or manager (López-Meri et al., 2020). Also, agricultural entrepreneurship offers a unique opportunity for individuals to control their time and design a personalised style of work. They are not under the influence of any superior as in the case of employees in an organisation. Thus, people venture into agriprenurship with the aim of gaining greater independence to implement their own approach to work (Alam et al., 2012). As one of the respondent noted:

“My husband's job was very intense, and I knew I could not do some jobs because I stay on the mainland and most of the jobs are in Island. I could not do a job that would take away the time I have for my children since my husband was already busy. So, I started thinking about what I can do. ...I would not have to work for anyone. So, I would design my business. Basically, that is how I started my farming business...I needed a job, I needed something that would give me time and farming popped up.”

The form of freedom enjoyed as an agriprenurs most of who are sole proprietors also cover resource control. These individuals decide how the resources of the business will be obtained, allocated and effectively managed without any form of unwarranted interference by a higher authority (Minarcine & Shaw, 2016). They make choices relating to how profits will be generated, used, the percentage that will be ploughed back to the business for expansion, and the share that will be earmarked for owner’s direct compensation (Eniola, 2021).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This empirical study has shown that Young Nigerians do perceive agricultural entrepreneurship positively. The question then is why is young agricultural engagement still very low? This means that positive perception alone is neither enough to drive intention to start agribusiness nor success in agribusiness. The differences in the relationship between family income and youth agriprenurship

perception vis-a-vis family income and youth agripreneurship intention indicates that financial capability is critical for translating positive perception into action. On the face of it, it seems that the poorer the family background, the more positive the agripreneurship perception, while the poorer the family background, the more negative is the intention to start an agribusiness. This contrast may be due to the fact that financial capability is a (conversion) factor for starting any business. However, more studies are needed to fully uncover these dynamics thus offering an area for future investigation. Nonetheless, the result suggests that government, financial institutions and other stakeholders should ensure that young Nigerians have access to financial resources to engender successful entrepreneurship functioning. It is against this backdrop that this study presents the need to look beyond training and perception, by creating a more comprehensive mechanism for boosting youth entrepreneurship engagement in Nigeria.

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